

RESEARCH ARTICLE

Enhancing Change Point Detection Through Key Actor Identification: A Study in Cryptocurrency Transactions Networks

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ABSTRACT This paper proposes a unified framework for analyzing cryptocurrency transaction networks, employing a composite approach that combines key actor identification and change point detection. At first, the framework identifies a representative key actor in a network of cryptocurrency transactions and retrieves its relevant transactions. Then, multiple features are extracted in the form of time series from its transaction history, providing an overview of its activity over time. In addition, feature selection is applied to reduce overlapping information among the extracted features and, finally, change point detection is utilized to identify time locations of significant changes in the selected features. To showcase the applicability of the proposed framework, four cryptocurrency transaction networks are used related to the tokens DAI, WLUNA, USTC and PAX. The analysis results indicate that the estimated change points often coincide with market events that may have influenced the network's transaction behavior. Overall, this paper presents a new approach for understanding the dynamics of cryptocurrency transaction networks, where, by identifying and examining their representative key actors, we aim to obtain a comprehensive characterization of its overall structure.

INDEX TERMS Cryptocurrency transaction networks, key actor identification, temporal features, change point detection.

I. INTRODUCTION

Over the past years, there has been an increasing interest in analytical methods and approaches that revolve around Decentralized Finance (DeFi), and specifically around cryptocurrency transactions, with the aim to improve transparency, enhance security, facilitate peer-to-peer transactions, reduce reliance on traditional financial intermediaries, and promote financial inclusion. Cryptocurrencies are virtual (digital) currencies that operate on decentralized networks based on blockchain technology, while the transactions performed using cryptocurrencies can be organically modeled through the use of graph data structures. In this context, the

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entities in a transaction graph (such as wallets or addresses) are represented by graph nodes, while the transactions between these entities are represented by graph edges.

Graph analysis methods offer a suited approach to gaining insights regarding the interactions of the entities in the underlying transaction dataset and can be naturally used to investigate these entities' relationships and corresponding topological features of the graph. For example, techniques related to cluster detection can aid in associating a group of entities to a common owner, while graph anomaly detection methods can be employed to detect transactions potentially linked to illicit activities, such as money laundering or fraudulent schemes. For instance, sudden spikes in transaction volume between otherwise unrelated entities might indicate attempts to obscure the origins of funds. Additionally,

detecting a high frequency of small transactions directed towards a single entity could signal a structuring strategy where transactions are deliberately kept below regulatory reporting thresholds to evade detection.

Key actor identification, in particular, is a graph analysis method that is used as a means of discovering graph nodes that exert influence or exhibit certain important topological features. These identified nodes are called ‘key actors’ and are usually characterized by a high value of a particular centrality measure, such as betweenness centrality or closeness centrality. By identifying and subsequently studying key actors in a graph, we aim to obtain a more comprehensive understanding of the graph’s structure and dynamics. For example, key actors can reveal the main hubs of activity, critical points for information flow, or potential vulnerabilities within the network, thereby providing valuable insights into the overall behavior and functionality of the graph.

Leveraging a transaction graph’s key actor information can enhance a subsequent time series analysis of the dataset. Specifically, focusing on the evolution of the defining features of a key actor node enables the identification of attribute shifts that concern the entire dataset, as well as the prediction of the overall network behavior. For example, in a communication network, observing changes in the communication patterns of a key actor might reveal shifts in the network’s flow of information, indicating emerging trends or potential disruptions. Similarly, in a financial network, tracking the transaction volumes and frequencies of key actors could help detect early signs of market volatility.

To this end, this work proposes a unified framework that analyzes the temporal evolution of a transactions network through a key actor-centric approach. The overall goal of the analysis is to enhance our understanding of the network’s dynamics, identifying early signs of significant changes or trends within the entire network influenced by market events. This approach contributes to uncovering the relationship between market volatility and transactions patterns, offering insights into the impact of market events on network behavior and flows of funds. Towards this direction, the framework focuses on the analysis of the most influential nodes, since key actors constitute critical indicators of the network’s overall operations.

Initially, a representative key actor from the transactions network is determined using a centrality measure aggregation ranking scheme. Following that, an analysis process is conducted on temporal features that are extracted from the key actor’s transactions. These temporal features result in time series that capture the evolution of the key actor’s metrics over time. By investigating the resulting time series through a multivariate change point detection approach, the framework identifies time locations of significant changes that occur during the evolution of the key actor’s transaction activity. This approach allows for an intuitive detection of critical shifts in network behavior, potentially triggered by market events, since key actors often have significant influence over the network structure. Subsequently, this may

serve as an efficient and streamlined way for gathering insights about graph’s structure and enabling more informed decision-making in response to emerging patterns or potential anomalies in the entire network.

To the best of our knowledge, this is the first work that incorporates key actor identification procedures to augment multivariate change point detection capabilities in cryptocurrency transactions. By integrating change point detection methods with key actor identification techniques for network analysis, we offer a unified framework on tracking the evolution of network dynamics over time, providing also a comprehensive tool for identifying significant changes in network activity through key-actor analysis, revealing potential market events that influence its behavior. Moreover, we also provide an end-to-end methodology for comprehensively characterizing the dynamics of cryptocurrency transaction networks.

Overall, the key contributions of this work are as follows: (1) We introduce a unified framework that integrates key actor identification with change point detection for cryptocurrency transaction networks, (2) we extract and refine time-series features derived from representative key actors, (3) we examine potential associations between detected change points and significant market events, and (4) we validate the framework’s versatility across four cryptocurrency networks ultimately showcasing how external factors may shape the evolution of cryptocurrency ecosystems.

The rest of the work is organized as follows. Section II reviews the relevant literature, while Section III formally defines the proposed framework. Section IV experimentally showcases the framework, while Section V provides an overall discussion of the results attained by the framework. Finally, Section VI concludes our work.

II. RELATED WORK

Over the past years, there have been significant contributions in the areas of key actor identification, as well as on applications stemming from time series analysis processes [18]. Given the extensive research volume in both fields, this literature review will focus on results pertaining to (or are applicable in) the context of blockchain and cryptocurrency transactions.

A. KEY ACTOR IDENTIFICATION

There has been growing research regarding the identification of influential nodes in graphs and several methods have been proposed. Early approaches in key actor identification, such as VoteRank [10] and its enhanced version VoteRank++ [5], primarily leveraged static characteristics of nodes underscoring the significance of local network structures and direct connections in evaluating node influence. With methods such as EnRenew [6] and RINF [19], key actor identification shifted towards embracing the complexity of information dynamics, such as information entropy and information spreading capability. The introduction of MCDE [7] and ECRM [8] methods represented a holistic approach to node

significance evaluation, combining core attributes with considerations of hierarchy, entropy, and interactions, paralleling the multi-faceted feature examination in cryptocurrency transaction analysis.

Recently, the Borda Count ranking scheme [9] has been employed for key actor identification [1], reflecting an attempt towards the integration of diverse metrics to distill influence and centrality. While identifying influential actors has been previously studied in the context of cryptocurrency transactions [3], [4], this is the first approach that combines static, dynamic, and graph-based features together with change point detection methods in a unified framework, to enrich the detection of important events within a transaction database.

B. TEMPORAL ANALYSIS OF CRYPTOCURRENCY TRANSACTIONS

Time series analysis approaches have been extensively applied to cryptocurrency data aiming to forecast their prices and returns. For example, the Autoregressive Integrated Moving Average (ARIMA) model has been applied [29] to predict the future value of Bitcoin by using the closing prices spanning a three-year period from September 1, 2015. A Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) neural network has been designed [32] to provide forecasts related to the Electro-Optical System (EOS) cryptocurrency's close price from November 9, 2017 to June 30, 2022. Moreover, the LSTM model was compared with the ARIMA model, concluding that the LSTM approach produced better predictions, at the cost of a longer time execution. Different prediction models were compared to predict Bitcoin's market movement [33] (namely ARIMA, Prophet (by Facebook), Random Forest, Random Forest Lagged-Auto-Regression, and Multi-Layer Perceptron (MLP) Neural Networks), resulting that the best overall model was the MLP deep neural net with 54% accuracy. Finally, in terms of time series analysis, attention has been paid to the prediction of the return volatility of cryptocurrencies. Towards this direction, several Generalized Autoregressive Conditional Heteroskedasticity (GARCH) models have been applied to seven cryptocurrencies [30]. Moreover, the performance of GARCH models was compared with stochastic volatility (SV) models in nine cryptocurrencies and resulted that SV models tended to perform better at longer horizons [31].

Temporal analysis has also been employed in examining networks of cryptocurrency transactions to gain insights on their structure, in addition to its application in analyzing crypto prices over time. For example, an analysis of bitcoin transaction activity found that there are weekly patterns in a bitcoin volume to the price per day graph [35]. Moreover, an analysis of three types of temporal graphs, i.e., user-to-user, contract-to-contract, and user-contract graphs from Ethereum transactions, observed a correlation between the size of user-to-user transaction graph and the average edge price in a time window [34]. In addition, unsupervised

learning techniques have been used to detect anomalies in the Bitcoin network [17]. The research emphasized the effectiveness of such methods in catching anomalies that traditional static analysis might miss, particularly those that evolve over time. An overview of the state-of-the-art literature on analyzing cryptocurrency transactions networks is presented in [36].

Another aspect of temporal analysis related to cryptocurrency transactions considers the exploitation of either address-based or wallet-based features and their evolution over time to identify illicit transactions and addresses. For instance, [37] extracted four dynamic features from Bitcoin transactions related to a known High-Yield Investment Program (HYIP), employing a sliding window of seven days and also calculated an anomaly score based on Principal Component Analysis. Similarly, [14] constructed temporal structures from time series, using an LSTM auto-encoder to encode discriminative temporal features for identifying illicit addresses and combined these with static and topological features for classification. Additionally, [16] proposed a change point detection framework useful as a digital forensics tool; 28 time series features were extracted from two Bitcoin entities involved in illicit transactions and statistically significant changes were identified in the transaction activity over time. The time locations of changes were linked to certain events, indicating a need of further investigation for the particular events.

Our work focuses on the analysis of temporal features related to cryptocurrency transactions networks aiming to gain further insights in networks evolution to provide early indicators of significant shifts in its behavior triggered by market events; this enables a better understanding of how external factors, like events that contribute to market volatility, influence network behavior, contributing to more effective monitoring and risk projection in the context of cryptocurrency transactions activities. Towards this direction, a graph analysis approach for key actor identification is combined with a time series analysis approach using a change point detection framework. Although there are existing studies on the analysis of cryptocurrency transactions that employ network analysis to understand the network dynamics, as well as on the inclusion of temporal graphs to assist in identifying anomalies as time evolves, our approach is distinct for the following reasons. First, the incorporation of key actor identification in the proposed framework results in pinpointing influential nodes that largely affect network dynamics, providing clearer insights into representative drivers of transactions flows, while change point detection estimates times where significant changes occur in the transaction behavior. This combination allows for providing a comprehensive view of both structural and temporal aspects in the blockchain, enhancing the monitoring of activities and the identification of transaction patterns that help revealing critical shifts in network dynamics to better understand the impact of external market events in network activity.

III. FRAMEWORK

This section introduces the proposed framework, beginning with a high-level overview before detailing each step of the process.

Let D be a transaction dataset where $\tau_{u,v}^t \in D$ signifies that there exists a transaction (i.e., exchange of a certain amount of cryptocurrency on a blockchain network) between entities u and v at timestamp t . Furthermore, let $G = (V, E)$ be a graph where the node set $V = \{u, v \mid \tau_{u,v}^t \in D\}$ corresponds to the entities that occur at any timestamp in D and the edge set $E = \{(u, v) \mid \tau_{u,v}^t \in D\}$ corresponds to the transactions between entities that occur at any timestamp in D . Our framework comprises a series of sequential steps that begin with receiving D and G as input and obtaining change points in the transaction activity as output.

Specifically, given G we evaluate the influence or importance of each node in the graph through a node ranking scheme based on the use of Borda score computation. Following that, let p be the graph's key actor node (i.e., the user with the highest Borda count value). The framework then retrieves all transactions relevant to p , i.e., $D_p = \{\tau_{u,v}^t \in D \mid u = p \vee v = p\}$ from D , and performs a feature extraction step where the activity of p is quantified over time across different metrics. The time series derived from the extracted features of p are then processed through a feature selection step to identify time series that exhibit comparable traits, discarding from the process time series with overlapping information. Finally, the selected time series serve as a multivariate input to the change point detection method employed in [28], which estimate time points of alteration in the evolution of the time series.

Figure 1 presents the overall methodology, outlining the key stages of the proposed framework from network construction to change point detection. In the remainder of the section we will explain in detail the mechanisms underlying each particular step.

A. KEY ACTOR IDENTIFICATION AND RETRIEVAL

The first step in the framework is concerned with the identification of key actors or influential nodes in the graph, i.e. nodes that possess topological characteristics that distinguish them from the rest of the network nodes. To this end, we measure the importance of each node using the centrality measure ranking aggregation approach proposed in [1]. Specifically, given $G = (V, E)$ and five centrality measures (degree, betweenness, closeness, eigenvector, pagerank), we evaluate each node's score for each of the five centrality measures. Following that, the respective score rankings for each centrality measure are defined as

$$\mathcal{R} = \langle \mathcal{R}^{DC}, \mathcal{R}^{BC}, \mathcal{R}^{CC}, \mathcal{R}^{EC}, \mathcal{R}^{PC} \rangle \quad (1)$$

where \mathcal{R}^i represents the ranking of all nodes according to centrality measure i . The Borda Count score of each node v

in G is thus defined as

$$S_v = \sum_{\mathcal{R}^i \in \mathcal{R}} (|V| - \mathcal{R}_v^i) \quad (2)$$

where \mathcal{R}_v^i corresponds to the rank of v in score ranking \mathcal{R}^i . By isolating the node p with the highest Borda count, i.e.

$$p = \operatorname{argmax}_i \{S_i\} \quad (3)$$

we obtain the key actor node of G . The relevant transactions D_p corresponding to the key actor p are then retrieved by filtering D and used as input to the next step in the workflow.

B. FEATURE EXTRACTION

Once the key node is identified and its transactions are retrieved, the framework proceeds with the extraction of multiple features from its transaction activity, monitoring their evolution over time. Table 1 presents the features extracted from the key actor's transaction data. These features are computed at specific time intervals, such as per day, to generate time series that depict the evolution of the transaction activity over time, providing a comprehensive overview of such activity. Features marked as 'received' or 'spent' indicate whether the key address is the recipient or sender in a transaction, respectively. Most of the features have also been utilised in [16] for the analysis of bitcoin transactions towards the detection of illicit activities, namely features 1-11, 14-20, and 24-30.

TABLE 1. Features extracted from key actors per certain time step.

No	Feature Name	Description
1	f_{TX}	The number of transactions per defined time step
2	$m_{balance}$	Mean balance of the entity
3	$m_{balance_USD}$	Mean balance of the entity in United States Dollars (USD)
4	$m_{received_USD}^{amount}$	Mean amount of received transactions in USD
5	$m_{spent_USD}^{amount}$	Mean amount of spent transactions in USD
6	$r_{received}$	Ratio of received transactions to all transactions
7	$r_{received}^{amount}$	Ratio of received amount over all transacted amount
8	$r_{received,spent}$	Ratio of received transactions to spent transactions
9	$r_{received,spent}^{amount}$	Ratio of received amount over the spent amount
10	r_{spent}	Ratio of spent transactions to all transactions
11	r_{spent}^{amount}	Ratio of spent amount over all transacted amount
12-21	$f_{i_received_USD}$	Frequency of received transactions where the amount (in USD) is: $10^{i-1} < USD \leq 10^i$ for $i \in \{-3, -2, -1, 0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6\}$
22-31	$f_{i_spent_USD}$	Frequency of spent transactions where the amount (in USD) is: $10^{i-1} < USD \leq 10^i$ for $i \in \{-3, -2, -1, 0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6\}$

FIGURE 1. Framework overview with each step showcased from left to right: (a) Network construction, (b) Key actor identification, (c) Retrieval of relevant transactions, (d) Feature extraction, (e) Feature selection, and (f) Change point detection.

C. FEATURE SELECTION

The third step of the proposed unified framework corresponds to the feature selection part, where a subset of features is chosen from those initially extracted. This subset forms the multivariate input to the change point analysis algorithm.

The rationale for the feature selection step is twofold. At first, the adopted approach requires the generation of 31 time series features, as listed at Table 1. If this number of features is further combined with time series of significant length, the combination could lead to a noticeable increase in both computational cost and the time it takes to perform the analysis. Secondly, feature selection also targets the removal of overlapping information among the features which do not add further value to the analysis. Consequently, our goal is to mitigate the computational cost and in parallel retain only those time series that enhance our understanding and reduce unnecessary overlap.

The adopted method for feature selection is based on a clustering approach, given that the clustering of features with similar characteristics can also potentially capture non-linear relationships between them that more traditional correlation-based methods might miss. Then, by selecting representative features from each cluster, dimensionality is effectively reduced while retaining diversity in the feature set. In our case, the extracted features from the second step of the analysis are clustered into homogeneous groups and the centres of the clusters serve as a multivariate input to the change point detection method applied in the final step of the unified framework. We utilize the *Partition Around Medoids* (PAM) clustering algorithm for this task whereby the identified central points of the formulated clusters are actual time series of the dataset that represent their cluster, named medoids, which makes this method more robust to outliers and, more importantly, the feature set that will then feed the change point analysis step is formulated by actual points of the dataset. A comprehensive description of this algorithm can be found in [23].

In this work, the PAM clustering approach is used with the Dynamic Time Warping (DTW) algorithm as the distance measure. DTW is a measure of similarity between two time series that vary in time or speed compared to other distances which are more suitable for static data (e.g., Euclidean distance). In particular, the DTW algorithm aims to compare two time series and search for the path that minimizes the total distance between corresponding points on the two sequences. Dynamic programming is used in order to find the optimal

path. A detailed description of the DTW algorithm can be found in [24].

Finally, to estimate the optimal number of clusters, we employ a validation method that assesses the compactness and the separation of the formulated clusters. Towards this direction, a range of clustering validity indices (CVIs) can be used, such as the Dunn index [25] and the Silhouette index [27]. A comprehensive study [26] illustrated that no single CVI clearly outperforms the others. However, they also observed that the Silhouette (SL) index often performs well across various contexts. Given this, along with the lack of strong evidence favoring any particular CVI, we use the SL index for our analysis, selecting the number of clusters that maximizes its value.

D. CHANGE POINT ANALYSIS

Change point analysis constitutes the final step of the proposed framework. In particular, the resulting time series from the feature selection step formulate the multivariate input to the change point detection (CPD) algorithm aiming at the estimation of time locations where significant changes occur in their evolution compared to their past behavior.

In our context, the CPD algorithm presented in [28] is used; this algorithm applies to multivariate time series, is nonparametric, and is based on the *E-Divisive* method. The multivariate approach allows for the exploitation of possible correlations that may exist among the time series of interest, while being nonparametric makes the framework more flexible, since we avoid the ambiguity of model fitting.

Let $\mathbf{X}_n = \{X_i : i = 1, 2, \dots, n\}$ and $\mathbf{Y}_m = \{Y_j : j = 1, 2, \dots, m\}$ be independent identical distributed (i.i.d.) samples from the distribution of X and $Y \in \mathbb{R}^d$, respectively, where n is the sample size of set \mathbf{X}_n , m is the sample size of set \mathbf{Y}_m , and d is the dimensionality of the space in which random vectors X, Y exist, such that $E|X|^\alpha, E|Y|^\alpha < \infty$ for some $\alpha \in (0, 2)$. An empirical divergence measure is defined as follows:

$$\hat{\varepsilon}(\mathbf{X}_n, \mathbf{Y}_m; a) = \frac{2}{mn} \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^m |X_i - Y_j|^a - \binom{n}{2}^{-1} \sum_{1 \leq i < k \leq n} |X_i - X_k|^a - \binom{m}{2}^{-1} \sum_{1 \leq j < k \leq m} |Y_j - Y_k|^a,$$

$a \in (0, 2)$. For the detection of a single change point, a scaled sample measure of the above divergence measure is defined as:

$$\hat{Q}(\mathbf{X}_n, \mathbf{Y}_m; a) = \frac{mn}{m+n} \hat{\varepsilon}(\mathbf{X}_n, \mathbf{Y}_m; a), \quad a \in (0, 2)$$

Let $Z_1, Z_2, \dots, Z_T \in \mathbb{R}^d$ be an independent sequence of observations, and let $1 \leq \tau < \kappa \leq T$ be constants, where τ, κ represent arbitrary indices within the sequence, and T denotes the length of the time series of observations. The sets $\mathbf{X}_\tau = \{Z_1, Z_2, \dots, Z_\tau\}$ and $\mathbf{Y}_\tau(\kappa) = \{Z_{\tau+1}, Z_{\tau+2}, \dots, Z_\kappa\}$ are defined, and a change point location $\hat{\tau}$ is estimated as

$$(\hat{\tau}, \hat{\kappa}) = \underset{(\tau, \kappa)}{\operatorname{argmax}} \hat{Q}(\mathbf{X}_\tau, \mathbf{Y}_\tau(\kappa); a)$$

To estimate multiple change points, the above technique is iteratively applied. Suppose that $k-1$ change points have been estimated at time locations $0 < \hat{\tau}_1 < \dots < \hat{\tau}_{k-1} < T$. These partition the observations into k clusters $\hat{C}_1, \dots, \hat{C}_k$, such that $\hat{C}_i = \{Z_{\hat{\tau}_{i-1}+1}, \dots, Z_{\hat{\tau}_i}\}$, in which $\hat{\tau}_0 = 0$ and $\hat{\tau}_k = T$. Given these clusters, the procedure for finding a single change point is applied to the observations within each of the k clusters. The corresponding test statistic for the k -th estimated change point is given by the relation $\hat{q}_k = \hat{Q}(\mathbf{X}_{\hat{C}_k}, \mathbf{Y}_{\hat{C}_k}(\hat{\kappa}_k); a)$, where $\hat{\tau}_k = \hat{\tau}(i)$ denotes the k th estimated change point located within cluster \hat{C}_i and $\hat{\kappa}_k = \hat{\kappa}(i)$ the corresponding constant. Moreover, a permutation test is used to determine the statistical significance of each change point (p -value) under the null hypothesis of no additional change points (R random permutations are performed). First, the observations within each cluster are permuted to create a new sequence of length T . The estimation process is then implemented again for the detection of change points in the permuted observations. This process is repeated, and after the l -th permutation of the observations, the test statistic $\hat{q}_k^{(l)}$ is recorded. An approximate p -value of the k -th estimated change point is defined as:

$$\#\{l : \hat{q}_k^{(l)} \geq \hat{q}_k\} / (R + 1)$$

Based on the *E-Divisive* method, once a change point location is estimated, the time series is partitioned into two clusters of observations. This process is iteratively applied to each cluster, leading to further segmentation until no additional statistically significant change points are detected. The statistical significance of a change point is determined via a permutation test, as described above.

Next, we showcase the applicability of the proposed unified framework to four different real-world networks of cryptocurrency transactions.

IV. APPLICATION ON REAL-WORLD DATASETS

In this section, we will experimentally validate the implementation of the proposed framework using four cryptocurrency transaction datasets and discuss our findings for each. Specifically, Section IV-A provides an overview of the experimental setup and the datasets used, while Section IV-B

reports characteristics (e.g., Borda count, number of transactions, etc.) of the identified key actors related to their network activity in each dataset. Sections IV-C, IV-D, IV-E and IV-F present our results for each of the four datasets respectively.

A. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

Our study utilizes the ‘‘Stablecoin ERC20 Transactions Dataset’’, a publicly available dataset from the Stanford Large Network Dataset Collection (SNAP) [11]. The dataset comprises transaction records of several stablecoins,¹ such as USTC and DAI, including WLUNA which is not a stablecoin, but it is a form of the LUNA classic token traded on the Ethereum blockchain. The structure of the dataset is illustrated in Table 2, where each row represents a single transaction and the columns provide the following attributes for the transactions:

- *block_number*: the block containing the transaction
- *transaction_index*: the position of the transaction within the block
- *from_address*: the sender’s address
- *to_address*: the recipient’s address
- *timestamp*: the time when the block containing the transaction was mined
- *contract_address*: the smart contract address of the token involved in the transaction (e.g., USTC, DAI)
- *value*: the number of tokens transferred in the transaction

TABLE 2. Structure of the ‘‘Stablecoin ERC20 Transactions Dataset’’.

block number	transaction index	from address	to address	timestamp	contract address	value
block1	index1	sender1	recipient1	time1	contract1	value1
block2	index2	sender2	recipient2	time2	contract2	value2
block3	index3	sender3	recipient3	time3	contract3	value3
...

The initial step in the preprocessing of the dataset involved filtering out the smart contracts associated with the dataset (see Table 2), since smart contracts represent transactions with different tokens. Therefore, we identified four principal smart contracts corresponding to four distinct cryptocurrency tokens: DAI, WLUNA, USTC, and PAX. This identification allowed us to separate the dataset into four subsets, each representing a network of transactions pertaining to one of the four aforementioned tokens.

DAI is a stablecoin cryptocurrency that aims to keep its value as close to one USD as possible through an automated system of smart contracts, on the Ethereum blockchain. Paxos Standard (PAX) stands as a digital dollar, akin to other stablecoins, engineered to provide a digital substitute for traditional currency; it merges the stability inherent in the dollar with the technological efficiency of blockchain, thereby offering users a modernized means of conducting transactions and storing value. TerraUSD (USTC) is a stablecoin initially pegged to the USD, created by Terraform

¹A stablecoin is a type of cryptocurrency that is designed to maintain a stable value relative to a specific asset.

TABLE 3. Dataset description.

Dataset	Nodes	Edges
DAI	328,036	720,936
WLUNA	104,758	180,714
USTC	48,487	95,559
PAX	12,790	19,487

Labs on the Terra blockchain. It aimed to maintain its peg through an algorithmic relationship with Terra's native token, LUNA, allowing for minting and burning processes to stabilize its price.² Wrapped LUNA (WLUNA) allows Terra's native token, LUNA (now referred to as LUNC in the context of Terra Classic), to be used on other blockchains by wrapping it into a token on that blockchain, maintaining the value of the original asset. This facilitates the use of LUNA in various DeFi applications outside its native ecosystem.

Following the dataset split, our analysis adopted a graph-based approach to represent the transactions within each stablecoin network. The transactions were modeled as a graph where each node represented a unique address, and the edges between nodes signified transactions between these addresses.

To construct each graph, we focus on the aggregation of transactions between addresses, effectively simplifying the dataset to highlight the existence of interactions regardless of their corresponding timestamp of occurrence. Specifically, we derive a graph by considering the union of transactions across all time instances. In this premise, the graph contains an edge from address v to address u if there is at least one transaction recorded between v and u at any given timestamp. Table 3 outlines the resulting graph data structures for each of the four datasets.

B. QUANTITATIVE OBSERVATIONS

Before presenting the framework's results in each of the four datasets, we provide a summary of quantitative observations that were obtained during the analysis process. Table 4 lists the key actors within each dataset³ along with the number of their transactions, corresponding Borda count, and time period between the first and the last transaction for that key actor.

In the following sections, we present the results of the application of the proposed methodology to four different networks of transactions related to the DAI, USTC, and PAX stablecoins, as well as to the WLUNA token.

C. ANALYSIS OF DAI TRANSACTIONS

In this section, we present the results from analyzing the transaction network of DAI stablecoin with the proposed framework.

²In finance, "pegged" refers to the practice of tying the value of one asset to another, typically a stable asset like a fiat currency or a commodity, to maintain a fixed exchange rate.

³The reported IDs have been pseudonymized to ensure the protection of personal data.

TABLE 4. Identified key actors with the highest Borda count within each transactions network.

Dataset	Address	Number of transactions	Borda count	Time period
DAI	552b811f0830bc90979c7a6dd4b65eb80c12d3e...	239,091	164,0176	Apr 1, 2022 - Nov 1, 2022
WLUNA	e17461ae72e504ed793fdb1a51c692de77d630d...	85,781	523,790	Apr 1, 2022 - Oct 12, 2022
USTC	6946f84c33bfcdb070503b32e9598c618d0c...	22,583	242,435	Apr 1, 2022 - Sept 8, 2022
PAX	7e41dbfd3522207a848954e779cc561e619a53c...	1,729	63,949	Apr 1, 2022 - Nov 1, 2022

TABLE 5. SL index values for different number of clusters in the key actor transactions of the DAI dataset.

No. of clusters	SL index
2	0.129
3	0.132
4	0.171
5	0.161
6	0.193
7	0.185
8	0.217
9	0.198
10	0.103

1) KEY ACTOR IDENTIFICATION

Borda count is calculated for each node in the transactions network of DAI stablecoin, resulting in the identification of the key actor address with the highest Borda count. Then, the transactions of the key actor address are retrieved, having 239,091 transactions, spanning the period from April 1, 2022 to November 1, 2022. Table 4 presents the relevant information on the identified key actor.

2) FEATURE EXTRACTION

The list of features reported in Table 1 is extracted from the transaction activity of the key actor address for the DAI dataset. This key actor address was active from April 1, 2022 to November 1, 2022, resulting in the construction of time series features with length $T = 213$ (days). In this case, feature 10 ($m_{balance_USD}$) is equal to feature 11 ($m_{balance}$), since the exchange rate between the DAI and USD is one-to-one. Therefore, 30 time series features are extracted in total with length $T = 213$ (days) each.

3) FEATURE SELECTION

Next, the extracted features are categorized into homogeneous groups based on the PAM clustering approach using the DTW distance. Then, the medoids time series of the constructed clusters are selected to formulate the input to the change point detection algorithm that follows. In this case, the optimal number of clusters is determined via the use of SL index, selecting the number of clusters that maximizes its value. The relevant results are presented in Table 5.

TABLE 6. Clusters and the relevant medoids for the DAI dataset.

Cluster	Features in cluster	Medoid feature	Feature name
1	6, 8	6	$r_{received}$
2	16, 17, 18, 26, 27, 28	27	$f_{2_spent_USD}$
3	10, 15, 25	15	$f_{0_received_USD}$
4	4, 5, 20, 30	4	$r_{received}^{amount}$
5	14, 24	14	$f_{-1_received_USD}$
6	3, 7, 9	9	$r_{received,spent}$
7	21, 31	21	$f_{6_received_USD}$
8	1, 10, 19, 29	29	$f_{4_spent_USD}$

Based on Table 5, the maximum value of the SL index corresponds to eight clusters; therefore, we proceed with the clustering of the extracted time series features into eight groups. The time series included in each cluster, as well as the corresponding medoids, are presented at Table 6.

4) CHANGE POINT DETECTION

The medoid time series of the clusters identified in Table 6 form the multivariate time series input to the change point detection algorithm described in Section III. The results of the change point analysis are presented in Table 7 and depicted graphically in Figure 2.

TABLE 7. Time locations of the estimated change points in the eight-dimensional time series for the DAI dataset with the corresponding significance values at 5% significance level.

No.	Time	Date	p-value
1	42	May 13, 2022	0.002
2	72	June 12, 2022	0.002
3	119	July 29, 2022	0.002
4	144	August 23, 2022	0.002
5	182	September 30, 2022	0.002

Some conclusions can be derived based on the outcomes of the application of the proposed framework to the DAI dataset. The first (statistically significant) change point is estimated at time location $t = 42$ (May 13, 2022) signifying a change in the transaction activity of the identified key actor compared to the previous period. This alteration in the transaction behavior may be linked to the LUNA collapse that occurred on May 12, 2023 and could have impacted the activity of the influential address. The period between the second estimated change point at $t = 72$ (June 12, 2022) and $t = 119$ (July 29, 2022) appears to have a more intense trend compared to the previous one. This upward trend is particularly observed in the medoid time series of the eighth cluster (i.e., $f_{4_spent_USD}$) related to the frequency of the spent transactions where the spent amount is greater than 1000 USD and lower than 10000 USD; cluster eight also involves the time series that represents the evolution of the frequency of the transactions over time. This upward trend may be partially related to some events in the market cap with positive impact that occurred in the beginning/mid of June 2022, such as the expansion of the USDT stablecoin onto the TEZOS blockchain⁴ and the deployment of 700 USD million

by TRON DAO RESERVE to support the stability of USDD stablecoin.⁵ Moreover, the fourth estimated change point at time location $t = 144$ (August 23, 2022) initiates a period with more intense transaction activity compared to the previous one. This could be linked to some events that occurred in late August and may have potentially affected the transaction activity of the key actor, such as the announcement of the release of USD coin version 2.0⁶ and the proposal of the “Endgame Plan” from the co-founder of MakerDao to protect the DAI stablecoin from potential attacks.⁷ Finally, the last estimated change point at $t = 182$ (September 30, 2022) signals a period with a decreasing trend in the transaction activity of the key actor, which could be partially linked to the announcement that the FTX suspended LUNA and UST deposits and withdrawals in mid September 2022.⁸

The analysis results in the DAI dataset indicate that links are identified between the time locations of the estimated change points and market events, implying that the changes in the key actor’s activity might be to some extent responsive to these occurrences. This insight suggests that the events are reflected in the evolution of the key actor’s activity, and subsequently in the network’s dynamics, since the key actor has influence on the other nodes. This may assist in the early identification of patterns and trends in the entire network of interest, as well as in the gaining of a deeper understanding of how significant events shape network behavior, leading to more informed decision making.

D. ANALYSIS OF WLUNA TRANSACTIONS

Similarly to the transactions of DAI dataset, we apply the proposed framework to the network of WLUNA transactions.

1) KEY ACTOR IDENTIFICATION

The key actor address with the highest Borda count is identified within the network of WLUNA transactions and then its transactions are retrieved. Based on the results, the key actor address is involved in 85,781 transactions, spanning the period from April 1, 2022 till October 12, 2022. The relevant information is presented in Table 4.

2) FEATURE EXTRACTION

The time series features listed in Table 1 are extracted from the transactions dataset of the identified key actor. Since the key actor was active from April 1, 2022 until September 8, 2022, this results in the construction of 31 time series with length $t = 194$ (days) each.

3) FEATURE SELECTION

Similarly to before, the values of the SL index for each number of clusters are reported in Table 8.

⁵<https://coingape.com/breaking-tron-deploys-700-mln-to-support-usdd-stablecoin/>

⁶<https://www.circle.com/blog/major-update-to-usd-coin-released-today-advancing-digital-dollar-stablecoin-usability-security>

⁷<https://decrypt.co/108858/one-does-not-simply-destroy-dai-maker-founders-endgame-proposal>

⁸<https://coingape.com/breaking-ftx-suspend-lunc-ustc-deposits-withdrawals>

⁴<https://tether.to/en/tether-tokens-usdt-to-launch-on-tezos/>

FIGURE 2. Time locations (vertical lines) of the estimated change points in the eight-dimensional time series for the DAI dataset.

TABLE 8. SL index values for different number of clusters in the key actor transactions of the WLUNA dataset.

No. of clusters	SL index
2	0.296
3	0.317
4	0.348
5	0.095
6	0.163
7	0.149
8	0.145
9	0.127
10	0.0985

The maximum value of the SL index corresponds to the grouping of the features into four clusters; therefore, we proceed with the formulation of the clusters, and the results are presented in Table 9.

4) CHANGE POINT DETECTION

Similarly to before, we perform change point analysis to the four-dimensional time series that is derived from the feature selection step; the results are reported in Table 10 and depicted graphically in Figure 3.

TABLE 9. Clusters and the relevant medoids for the WLUNA dataset.

Cluster	Features in cluster	Medoid feature	Feature name
1	1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 9, 18, 19, 20, 21, 28, 29, 30, 31	1	f_{TX}
2	6, 7, 8	6	$r_{received}$
3	10, 11,	10	r_{spent}
4	14, 15, 16, 17, 24, 25, 26, 27	15	$f_{0_received_USD}$

TABLE 10. Time locations of the estimated change points in the four-dimensional time series for the WLUNA dataset with the corresponding significance values at 5% significance level.

No.	Time	Date	p-value
1	41	May 12, 2022	0.002
2	61	June 1, 2022	0.002
3	163	September 11, 2022	0.002

Similarly to the DAI dataset, some observations can be derived based on the analysis of the WLUNA transactions. The first estimated change point at $t = 41$ (May 12, 2022) initiates a period with different transaction activity from the

FIGURE 3. Time locations (vertical lines) of the estimated change points in the four-dimensional time series for the WLUNA dataset.

key actor’s side. In particular, an increasing trend is depicted for the frequency of transactions and a decreasing one for the frequency of received transactions where the transacted amount lies between 0.1 USD and 1 USD. This differentiation may be related to the LUNA collapse on May 12, 2022 that could have impacted the key actor’s transaction activity. Moreover, the second estimated change point at $t = 61$ (June 1, 2022) initiates a period with quite low transaction activity compared to the previous one. A similar behavior is initiated by the third estimated change point at $t = 163$ (September 11, 2022), where a period with quite low transaction activity is also signified.

E. ANALYSIS OF USTC TRANSACTIONS

In this section, the proposed framework is applied to the network of transactions of the USTC stablecoin.

1) KEY ACTOR IDENTIFICATION

As in the previous cases, the address with the maximum Borda count value is identified and its transactions are retrieved from the USTC dataset. The identified key actor address is involved in 22,583 transactions spanning the period

from April 1, 2022 till September 8, 2022. The relevant info is presented in Table 4.

2) FEATURE EXTRACTION

The features listed in Table 1 are extracted from the transaction activity of the identified key actor address resulting in the construction of 31 time series with length $t = 160$ each.

3) FEATURE SELECTION

The SL index is calculated for each cluster that resulted from the PAM method, and the maximum value corresponds to the use of four clusters, as illustrated in Table 11.

Therefore, we proceed with the grouping of the extracted features into four clusters, reported in Table 12.

4) CHANGE POINT DETECTION

Similar to before, the results of the change point analysis in the four-dimensional time series resulted from the feature selection step are presented in Table 13 and graphically in Figure 4.

Based on the output of the change point analysis in the four dimensional time series, three changes points are estimated.

FIGURE 4. Time locations (vertical lines) of the estimated change points in the four-dimensional time series for the USTC dataset.

TABLE 11. SL index values for different number of clusters in the key actor transactions of the USTC dataset.

No. of clusters	SL index
2	0.231
3	0.258
4	0.302
5	0.223
6	0.0928
7	0.0725
8	0.184
9	0.0749
10	0.24

The first one is estimated at time $t = 37$ (May 8, 2022), that initiates a period with more active transaction activity compared to the past. This differentiation could be related to the LUNA crash that occurred in May 2022 and possibly affected the key actor’s transaction activity. Then, the period between the second estimated point at time $t = 63$ (June 3, 2022) and the third one at time $t = 145$ (August 2, 2022) is characterized by a quite low transaction activity. Finally, the last period initiated at time $t = 145$ showcases similarly low transaction activity in which the ratio of received transactions

TABLE 12. Clusters and the relevant medoids for the USTC dataset.

Cluster	Features in cluster	Medoid feature	Feature name
1	1, 16, 17,18, 19, 20, 21, 26, 27,28, 29, 30, 31	1	f_{TX}
2	6, 7, 8, 10	6	$r_{received}$
3	11	11	r_{spent}
4	2, 3, 4, 5, 9, 14, 15, 24, 25	9	$r_{received,spent}$

TABLE 13. Time locations of the estimated change points in the four-dimensional time series for the USTC dataset with the corresponding significance values at 5% significance level.

No.	Time	Date	p-value
1	37	May 8, 2022	0.002
3	63	June 3, 2022	0.008
3	145	August 24, 2022	0.008

and the relevant received amount in USD fluctuates in the reported transactions. This low transaction activity may be partially related to events that occurred during this period

(e.g., suspension of deposits and withdrawals for USTC in early September⁹).

F. ANALYSIS OF PAX TRANSACTIONS

In this section, we apply the proposed framework to the network of transactions that concerns the PAX stablecoin.

1) KEY ACTOR IDENTIFICATION

The Borda count is calculated for every node in the dataset, identifying the one that achieves the highest value. The transactions of this key actor address are retrieved, covering the period from April 1, 2022 to November 1, 2022. During this period, the address was involved in 1,729 transactions. The relevant information is illustrated in Table 4.

2) FEATURE EXTRACTION

Next, we proceed with the extraction of the time series features listed in Table 1 from the transaction activity of the identified key actor. Similarly to the DAI dataset, the exchange rate between PAX crypto and USD is one-to-one; therefore, features 10 and 11 are the same. 30 time series features are extracted with length $t = 213$ (days) each, capturing the evolution of the transaction history of the key actor address in the PAX dataset.

3) FEATURE SELECTION

The DTW distance is used for the implementation of the PAM clustering method, and the best number of clusters is determined based on the maximum value of the SL index. The values of the SL index are calculated, and the maximum value corresponds to eight clusters, as illustrated in Table 14; therefore, we group the extracted features into eight clusters, and the results are reported in Table 15.

TABLE 14. SL index values for different number of clusters in the key actor transactions of the PAX dataset.

No. of clusters	SL index
2	0.197
3	0.207
4	0.0871
5	-0.0272
6	0.211
7	0.128
8	0.213
9	0.186
10	0.0929

4) CHANGE POINT DETECTION

The results of the change point analysis on the eight-dimensional time series derived from the feature selection step are presented in Table 16, and depicted graphically in Figure 5.

The first change point is estimated at time $t = 34$ (May 5, 2022) initiating an increasing trend in the key

⁹<https://www.binance.com/en/support/announcement/notice-on-deposits-and-withdrawals-of-terra-classic-lunc-and-terraclassicusd-ustc-f14b7fc184b74237a9e68796a2939dec>

TABLE 15. Clusters and the relevant medoids for the PAX dataset.

Cluster	Features in cluster	Medoid feature	Feature name
1	6, 7, 8, 11, 11	6	$r_{received}$
2	16, 19, 26	16	$f_{1_received_USD}$
3	27, 28	27	$f_{2_spent_USD}$
4	1	1	f_{TX}
5	5, 20, 30	20	$f_{5_spent_USD}$
6	10	10	r_{spent}
7	17, 18, 29	18	$f_{3_received_USD}$
8	2, 4, 9, 21, 31	31	$f_{6_spent_USD}$

TABLE 16. Time locations of the estimated change points in the eight-dimensional time series for the PAX dataset with the corresponding significance values at 5% significance level.

No.	Time	Date	p-value
1	34	May 5, 2022	0.002
2	102	July 12, 2022	0.002
3	159	September 7, 2022	0.002
4	184	October 2, 2022	0.014

actor's transaction activity compared to the past. This may be partially related to the event of LUNA crash that occurred in May 2022, and may have triggered the change. The remaining periods formulated by the estimated change points illustrate either a decreasing trend in the key actor's transaction activity (for example the period between the time $t = 159$ (September 7, 2022) and $t = 184$ (October 2, 2022) or a slightly increasing one compared to the past (for example the period between $t = 184$ (October 2, 2022) until $t = 213$ (November 1, 2022)). These identified changes in the key actor's transaction behavior may be partially linked to event occurrences that could have triggered them, such as the suspension of deposits and withdrawals for LUNC and USTC in September 2022¹⁰ or the USTC significant surge in October 2022.¹¹

V. DISCUSSION

This paper proposes a unified framework for the analysis of network's transactions based on temporal features, combining a key actor identification method with a change point detection approach. The proposed framework aims to identify time locations in the transactions network where significant changes have occurred to gain further insights in the market behavior. Moreover, possible links are identified between the time instances of significant changes and event occurrences in the market activity that may have influenced these changes. For this purpose, the analysis focuses on the key actor's transaction behavior in the network by extracting multiple time series features related to its transaction activity; the relevant features are listed at Table 1.

In other words, instead of analysing multiple nodes of the transactions' network to deepen our understanding of the impact of market events onto them, the key actor's activity

¹⁰<https://www.binance.com/en/support/announcement/notice-on-deposits-and-withdrawals-of-terra-classic-lunc-and-terraclassicusd-ustc-f14b7fc184b74237a9e68796a2939dec>

¹¹<https://capital.com/terraclassic-usd-ustc-re-peg-zaradar-proposal-detail>

FIGURE 5. Time locations (vertical lines) of the estimated change points in the eight-dimensional time series for the PAX dataset.

is examined, since it constitutes an influential node for the others. Therefore, the first step of analysis in the proposed framework includes the identification of the key actor node within the network of transactions; this identification is based on the calculation of the Borda Count. Note, that the identification of key actors is inherently tied to network size and on large-scale transaction networks, computational costs may become prohibitive, potentially requiring optimized or specialized graph processing solutions. Then, the transactions of the node with the highest Borda Count are retrieved and change point analysis is implemented in time series features that capture the dynamic evolution of the key actor's transaction behavior. The adopted algorithm for change point detection has quadratic time complexity in the length of the time series. Therefore, more time-efficient CPD methods could be employed for very large time series, provided that they are non-parametric and capable of handling multivariate data.

The unified framework is applied to four transaction networks of the tokens DAI, WLUNA, USTC and PAX. Based on the analysis results in all datasets, we observe that the time locations of the estimated change points in

the transaction activity of each key actor partially coincide with occurrences of events in the market that could possibly trigger -to some extent- these changes. This observation is more obvious when considering the first estimated change point in all cases (May 2022), which coincides temporally with the LUNA crash. This event caused a shock in the ecosystem with USTC losing its peg and WLUNA price falling from 120 USD to 0 USD. The analysis result indicates that the changes triggered by such a significant event in the ecosystem (market) are reflected in the key actor's transaction activity, therefore in the network's behavior, given that the key actor functions as an influence on the other nodes. By understanding these influences over time, we can better identify emerging patterns and trends across the entire network, enabling more informed decision-making processes in future developments.

In addition to the aforementioned observations, another aspect of the utility of the proposed framework in the context of financial transactions with cryptocurrencies is related to the early identification of irregular transaction behavior that could suggest fraudulent activities. Due to the pseudo-anonymity that crypto transactions offer, they

have been widely used to support illicit activities, such as money laundering [20], Ponzi schemes [21], and darknet markets [22]. In such cases, network analysis focusing on the activity analysis of the most influential node and its evolution over time may assist in the uncovering of potential fraud based on targeted investigations, since key actors can serve as indicators of network's operations.

VI. CONCLUSION

This work presented a unified framework for analyzing cryptocurrency transaction networks based on temporal features. The framework revolves around identifying a key actor within the network and then investigating the evolution of its transaction behavior over time. By employing an approach that combines key actor identification, feature extraction, feature selection, and change point analysis, the framework offers valuable insight into the network's dynamics. The application of the framework to four real-world datasets demonstrated its effectiveness in linking significant changes in the key actor's transaction activity to real-world events impacting the market. This highlights the framework's potential to bridge the gap between network behavior and external influences.

Future work could explore the integration of additional features in the feature extraction step capturing more information about the evolution of the transaction activity, as well as alternative key actor identification approaches to further enhance the framework's capabilities. Furthermore, causal inference methods could enhance the interpretability of connections between change point detections and market events. Finally, the adaptability of the proposed framework could also be validated across other transactions networks related to more volatile cryptocurrencies compared to stablecoins (e.g. Bitcoin, Ethereum, etc.).

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